

Table 1. Amylose content in endosperm of Hexi 4, grown at 5 locations with different altitudes in Yunnan Province, China.

Location	Altitude (m)	Average daily temperature in July (°C)	Amylose content (%)
Shunghshao	2140	18.6	19.8
Kunming	1916	19.8	18.9
Yuxi	1637	20.9	16.4
Yiliang	1550	21.7	16.4
Huanian	1000	24.3	15.4

Table 2. Amylose content in endosperm of mutant lines induced by N-methyl-N-nitrosourea treatment in Hexi 4.

Mutant or cultivar	Origin	Amylose content (%)
Hexi 4	Yunnan	20.1
94YM01 (dull)	Mutant	11.3
94YM02 (waxy)	Mutant	1.0
Koshihikari ^a	Japan	16.5
Nipponbare ^b	Japan	21.5

^aMost popular variety in Japan, has good eating quality.
^bUsed as standard for eating quality tests in Japan.

YAAS Crop Germplasm Institute. So we tried to induce low-amylose mutants by treating the fertilized eggs of a nonwaxy cultivar, Hexi 4, with N-methyl-N-nitrosourea (Table 2). We obtained two mutants, one of which was waxy and the other with very low amylose or dull endosperm. The mutant lines and Hexi 4 only differed slightly in heading time, plant height, and plant type. These lines are useful for improving the quality of japonica rice cultivated in the high altitudes of the subtropics and tropics. ■

Gan Wan Xian 19: high-yielding indica rice variety with improved grain quality

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The Jiang Xi Provincial Seedboard released Gan Wan Xian 19 in 1992. It is a new semidwarf indica rice variety derived from the cross between Hei Shi Tou, a traditional variety, and F4084, a strain from the cross IR2061/Ai Gan Nuo/Ru Wei Tao. It is suitable for late sowing in the double-cropped area of southern China.

Gan Wan Xian 19 is 95-102 cm in height and has strong stems. It matures in 134 d and has high yield potential under good irrigation and management conditions. In regional trials, the average yield was 6.8 t/ha, 11.6% more than that of M112, a local check in southern China. The highest yield obtained was 8.7 t/ha in the Huzhou region of central Jiangxi in 1993.

The variety possesses resistance to blast, bacterial blight, and whitebacked planthopper. It has tolerance for water

Table 1. Reaction^a of Gan Wan Xian 19 to blast, bacterial blight, and whitebacked planthopper.

Province ^{b/} institute	Leaf blast		Neck blast		Bacterial blight		Whitebacked planthopper	
	Rating	Reaction ^c	Rating	Reaction ^c	Rating	Reaction ^c	Rating	Reaction ^c
Zhejiang	5	S	3	MR	-	-	-	-
Yunnan	3	MR	3	MR	-	-	-	-
Hunan	2	MR	0	HR	-	-	-	-
Guandong	5	S	0	HR	3.7	R-MR	-	-
Jilin	3	MR	-	-	-	-	-	-
Jianmu	-	-	-	-	2.9	HR-R	-	-
China National Rice Research Institute	-	-	-	-	5.7	MR-S	3	R

^aScored using a 0-9 scale for leaf blast, and a 0, 1, 3, 5, 7, 9 scale for neck blast, bacterial blight, and whitebacked planthopper. ^bData from the plant protection Institute of each province. ^cS = susceptible, MR = moderately resistant, R = resistant, HR = highly resistant.

submergence in the areas where floods are frequent (Table 1).

Gan Wan Xian 19 has long, slender, translucent grains with intermediate amylose content, low gelatinization temperature, and soft gel consistency. It won a silver prize for its high quality at the First China Agricultural Product Exposition in October 1992 (Table 2).

The variety was grown on 66,000 ha in Jiang Xi in 1993 and has been spreading quickly in other parts of southern China. ■

Table 2. Quality characteristics of Gan Wan Xian 19.1992.

Characteristic	Mean
1,000-grain wt (g)	26.0
Brown rice (%)	79.8
Milled rice recovery (%)	73.1
Head rice (%)	55.3
Kernel length (mm)	7.1
Length-width ratio	3.6
Chalky kernel (%)	8.0
Area with chalkiness (%)	1.7
Amylose content (%)	21.3
Alkali spreading value	7.0
Gel consistency (mm)	76.0
Protein content of brown rice (%)	8.2

Physical, milling, chemical, and cooking characters of some rice cultivars in Tamil Nadu, India

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Growers, traders, millers, and consumers prefer different rice cultivars because of their grain yield and quality characters. We attempted to catalog certain physical, milling, chemical, and cooking characters in 16 rice cultivars commonly grown in Tamil Nadu, India.

Nine of these cultivars are short-duration (105-120 d), six are medium-

duration (121-140 d), and one is long-duration (more than 145 d). All are recommended for the lowland ecosystem. The short-duration cultivars were grown in 1992 dry season (Jun-Sep), and the medium- and long-duration varieties in 1992-93 wet season (Aug-Feb), following recommended practices. Grain was harvested, cleaned, and dried to 14%

Physical, milling, chemical, and cooking characters of 16 rice varieties. Tamil Nadu, India. 1992-93.

Variety	Duration (d)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Kernel length (mm)	Kernel breadth (mm)	Kernel thickness (mm)	L-B ratio	Kernel length	Kernel shape	Kernel length after cooking (mm)	Kernel breadth after cooking (mm)
IR50	105	19.3	6.3	2.0	1.6	3.1	Medium	Slender	9.5	3.0
TKM9	105	25.0	5.9	2.7	1.8	2.2	Medium	Medium	9.2	3.9
ADT37	105	20.5	5.1	2.7	1.5	1.9	Short	Bold	8.7	3.7
ADT36	110	21.2	6.1	2.3	1.6	2.7	Medium	Medium	10.3	3.3
ADT41	110	24.2	8.3	1.9	1.6	4.3	Extra long	Slender	11.7	2.9
ADT42	110	25.0	6.3	2.3	1.7	2.7	Medium	Medium	10.1	3.5
ASD16	110	24.2	5.7	2.6	1.8	2.2	Medium	Medium	8.1	3.8
ASD18	110	21.1	6.2	2.2	1.6	2.8	Medium	Medium	9.2	3.3
IR64	120	25.3	7.1	2.1	1.7	3.7	Long	Slender	10.6	3.3
ADT39	125	19.0	5.9	2.3	1.6	2.6	Medium	Medium	9.2	2.8
ADT38	135	22.7	6.8	2.2	1.7	3.1	Long	Slender	10.0	3.4
IR20	135	21.6	6.1	2.3	1.7	2.6	Medium	Medium	9.7	3.4
Co 43	135	22.6	6.0	2.4	1.7	2.6	Medium	Medium	9.5	3.7
Co 45	135	26.1	7.4	2.3	1.8	3.2	Long	Slender	12.0	3.5
Improved White Ponni	135	18.1	5.9	2.1	1.6	2.8	Medium	Medium	10.3	3.3
CR1009	155	22.8	5.1	2.7	1.9	1.9	Short	bold	8.5	3.9
\bar{X}	121.25	22.5	6.3	2.3	1.7	2.8	-	-	9.8	3.4
SD	3.85	1.8	0.9	0.5	0.3	0.8	-	-	1.0	0.6
CV (%)	3.18	8.0	14.1	20.8	19.2	28.1	-	-	10.3	16.4

Variety	Linear elongation ratio	Breadth-wise expansion	Elongation index	Alkali digestion score ^a	Amylose (%)	Water uptake 100 (ml)	Volume expansion	Brown rice (%)	Milling (%)	Head rice recovery (%)
IR50	1.6	1.4	1.1	3	23.2	220	4.2	74.0	68.0	50.0
TKM9	1.6	1.5	1.1	6	28.0	200	3.9	77.6	72.8	48.5
ADT37	1.6	1.4	1.2	2	24.8	280	5.0	79.2	70.4	52.4
ADT36	1.7	1.3	1.3	2	29.6	200	4.0	79.2	72.8	51.2
ADT41	1.5	1.5	1.0	5	16.0	260	4.7	72.8	66.8	53.2
ADT42	1.6	1.5	1.1	2	28.8	220	4.1	79.2	76.6	56.8
ASD16	1.6	1.4	1.2	2	24.8	180	3.9	78.4	72.0	64.0
ASD18	1.6	1.4	1.1	3	22.4	280	5.0	77.2	69.2	47.9
IR64	1.5	1.5	1.0	2	21.2	200	3.9	76.8	72.4	62.0
ADT39	1.6	1.4	1.2	3	24.0	200	3.6	80.0	76.0	57.2
ADT38	1.5	1.5	1.0	2	24.0	240	4.5	78.4	74.4	64.4
IR20	1.7	1.5	1.1	2	23.2	260	4.6	79.2	76.0	55.6
Co 43	1.6	1.5	1.1	3	32.4	200	3.9	78.4	74.0	59.2
Co 45	1.7	1.5	1.1	7	23.2	180	3.7	78.4	73.6	46.8
Improved White Ponni	1.8	1.5	1.2	3	22.4	260	4.6	76.4	72.4	50.4
CR1009	1.7	1.5	1.2	3	32.4	280	4.6	76.8	72.4	51.0
\bar{X}	1.6	1.5	1.1	3.1	25.0	228.8	4.3	77.6	72.5	54.4
SD	0.3	0.2	0.3	1.2	2.0	5.9	0.7	1.4	1.6	2.4
CV (%)	18.8	15.2	24.1	39.1	8.2	2.6	15.7	1.8	2.3	4.3

^aBased on the spreading scale of 1-7.

moisture content. Samples were drawn 1 mo after harvest. The methods described in the *Standard evaluation system of rice*, Juliano and Perez (1984), Pillaiyar and Mohandass (1981), and the standard procedures recommended for determining cooking qualities by Bhattacharya and Sowbhagya (1972) were used with two replicates (see table).

Kernels of ADT41, an aromatic fine rice, were extra long and slender. Kernels of IR64, ADT38, and Co 45 were long and slender, while those of ADT37 and CR1009 were short and bold. IR50

had medium slender kernels and the rest had medium kernel length and shape.

Co 45 and IR64 had the heaviest 1,000-grain weights and Improved White Ponni and ADT39, the lightest.

High mean values for linear elongation ratio and elongation index coupled with low mean values for breadthwise expansion ratio result in longer cooked rice grains with the least breadthwise swelling, giving a good appearance. These characters were favorably combined in ADT36, Improved White Ponni, and ADT39 (medium kernel length and

shape) and in ADT37 (short and bold). But the three long slender and one extra long slender genotypes showed similar values for linear elongation and breadthwise expansion ratios (see table).

Co 45, TKM9, and ADT41 had high alkali digestion scores, and the other genotypes had low mean values.

CR1009, Co 43, ADT36, ADT42, TKM9, ADT37, and ASD16 had high amylose content (more than 24%) and ADT41 had a very low content (16%). The others had intermediate amylose content.

ASD16 and Co 45 took up the least amount of water; ADT37, ASD18, and CR1009 took up the most. However, ADT37 and ASD18 had the highest values for volume expansion and ADT39 the least. Low water uptake and high volume expansion were noted in ADT42.

Head rice recovery was highest in ADT38 followed by ASD16 and IR64 (more than 60%). It was very low in

Co 45, ASD18, and TKM9 (less than 50%). ADT41 recorded a low percentage of brown rice (72.8%), with other genotypes ranging from 74.0 to 80.0%.

Milling and head rice recovery in the genotypes, however, were not proportionate to their respective hulling percentages.

The brown rice to milling difference is indicative of the quantity of bran and germ removed from the kernels. It was

highest in ADT37 (8.8%) and lowest in ADT42 (2.6%).

The fewest brokeners were in ASD 16 (8.0%) and the most in Co 45 (26.8%). The genotypes studied possessed more variability for gelatinization temperature, Length-breadth ratio, elongation index, and kernel breadth, indicating the possibility of the genetic improvement of these grain quality traits. ■

Pest resistance—diseases

Genetic diversity in *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzicola*

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Bacterial leaf streak (BLS), caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzicola*, is an increasing problem in rice production in tropical and subtropical Asia. Losses can be as high as 17% depending on the cultivar and climatic conditions. In China, BLS has recently become so severe that the pathogen has been placed on the quarantine list of some provinces. Many plots on the IRRI farm and in nearby farmers' fields have been heavily infected during the past two wet seasons.

Past studies have shown that *X. oryzae* pv. *oryzicola* exhibits a wide and continuous range of virulence. No clear differential interactions have been established. In this study, we determined the haplotypic diversity of *X. oryzae* pv. *oryzicola* and explored the relationships between haplotype and pathogen aggressiveness. This may be useful in allowing the selection of pathogen strains for screening and characterizing sources of resistance to BLS.

We evaluated the genetic diversity of a group of 124 *X. oryzae* pv. *oryzicola* strains between 1972 and 1990 from different regions of the Philippines. Diversity was estimated from data obtained by restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) (Fig. 1a) and *Pst*I

1. a) DNA hybridization profiles obtained using pR41 as the probe. b) DNA banding patterns based on *Pst*I restriction digestion.